

SOME ASPECTS OF SELF-DEVELOPMENT AND SELF-KNOWLEDGE, AND EFFECTIVE ASSESSMENT METHODS

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Abstract. *The implementation of a human approach to theirs as individuals in the educational process consists in providing it with pedagogical technologies, the main bug of the u the process of training learning process, the communicative basis of which is integrated into the individual.*

Keywords: *implementation, human approach, individuals, educational process, consists, providing, pedagogical technologies, process of training, learning process, communicative, basis of which is integrated.*

Workplace training aims to provide safety and opportunities to mobilize and protect life. It is also necessary to look for ways to use these opportunities for the ideal, all-round development of the reader's personality. The implementation of a humane approach to students as individuals in the educational process is to provide it with pedagogical technologies, the main feature of the educational process, the communicative basis of which is integrated into the personality.

This approach embodies the ideas in itself:

- approaching the personality of the student from a new point of view is the manifestation of education as a goal, ensuring that the educational process is integrated into the personality;
- humanization and democratization of pedagogical relations;
- it is necessary to abandon methods that do not give results in the modern educational process;
- a new characteristic of an individual approach;
- The personality of the student, the formation of himself in a positive aspect, etc.

The approach to the personality of the student from a new point of view is manifested in the following:

- to ensure the full development of students as a person in the educational process;
- to achieve the functioning of the pedagogical process as a subject of students' activity;
- that the main goal was the development of students in the educational process;
- to recognize the merits of each student and his faith in his abilities;
- positive qualities necessary for the personality of the student:
 - Compassion, kindness, diligence. create favorable pedagogical conditions for the manifestation of conscientiousness, the possession of civic positivity, etc.

The humanization of pedagogical relations and the preparation of personal relations for democratization should become the main factor determining the results of the educational process. Below are human relations to students, which in cases of manifestation should be:

- a) We must approach students with love and show interest in their future life;
- b) trust students, be ready for communication and humility with them, show mastery in this area;
- c) refrain from direct coercion of students;

d) believe in the prospects of uniting students to acquire positive qualities, values, folk culture;

e) be patient with the shortcomings, whims of students, show a tolerant attitude, etc.

Establishing democratic relationships with students is reflected in the following:

a) ensuring equal rights for teachers and students;

b) recognition that students have freedom of choice;

c) recognition of the rights of students who have their own point of view and their mistakes;

d) comply with the Child Protection Conventions in dealing with students;

e) give direction to students;

f) do not control students, but together with them you perform an action;

g) do not force students, but convince them;

j) do not order students, but organize their activities;

g) not to impose restrictions on students, but to provide him with the opportunity of free choice.

Within the framework of pedagogical cooperation, the creation of a learning environment without coercion of the student student has its own essence. The fact that the core content of the new relationship is not inhuman must be free from coercion that does not produce results. The main problems in this lie not in the absolutization of principles, but in the deeply considered measures used. It is impossible to completely abandon coercion in the educational process. But the system of social restrictions should be well mastered by the educator. Wrong education leads the student to insults, beaten, and this slows down his development and becomes the basis for the formation of a hostile mood in the individual. Teachers need to give up their own personal coercion, which hinders the development of students.

Non-coercive learning is characterized by the following characteristics:

a) the presence of a requirement that does not lead to coercion in a case based on trust;

b) born interests in connection with training;

c) changes in desire that lead to coercion to success;

g) create conditions for the independence and free functioning of students;

d) make demands on students every time through the student community, etc. Within the framework of educational pedagogy, the principle of an individual approach to students has its own new description. The moral of this individual approach is that in the education system, not from the subject of study to students, but, on the contrary, they are required to act depending on the subject of study. In this case, it is necessary to accurately assess the capabilities of students. Only when they depend on their intellect will it be appropriate to acquire knowledge.

Such an educational process should develop students, improve and enrich their knowledge. The new concept of individual approach embodies the following:

- students with an average level of proficiency refrain from unnecessary direction;

- search for the best personality traits of students;

- active application of methods of pedagogical and psychological diagnostics of personality;

- the interests of students, their merits, their cohesion on the way to a specific goal, increased self-awareness, qualities of their character, features of their way of thinking are revealed.

- obtaining the characteristics of the student in the educational process;

- predict the development of the student's personality;

- designing individual development programs for students and making regular adjustments, etc.

On this basis, students develop a sense of self-development and self-awareness of a positive nature. Self-consciousness is the identity of the individual, he himself embodies realized and unpurified ideas. Based on this, in behavior, he is an authority figure. During the educational training of students, the basis of the development of the mechanism appears.

A positive, uplifting sense of self in education gives students the opportunity to succeed, to work effectively, to show their positive qualities. The negative state kills their achievements in order to be complete, it degrades the results and this will lay the foundation for a change in character.

In addition to self-improvement, self-development is manifested through practice and research:

- **Practice** is expressed in the search for personal development methods, curricula, assessment systems, tools and techniques.

- As a field of research, self-development topics appear in magazines, books and websites in the fields of education, management, human development economics.

When we talk about self-development, we should also say that it includes mentoring. If you have mastered pedagogical techniques and are able to influence students in such a way that they progress as individuals, then you yourself are growing.

Self-knowledge must be painful sometimes if you don't want to live your whole life with your head in the sand. Spend your life being completely honest and open with yourself.

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